

SHORE

Empower students as the agents of change

D6.4 Second public report on the outcome of the open calls

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F6S

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Full name
NEBS	Network of European Blue Schools

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Executive summary

This document presents the SHORE Open Call#2 through its' application process and results, as well as the SHORE Open Call#2 statistics and selected school projects overview in the following manner:

- Section 1 presents Background of the SHORE Open Calls
- Section 2 presents SHORE - Open Call #2 and its process;
- Section 3 presents SHORE - Open Call #2 analytics of the finalised applications;
- Section 4 presents SHORE - Open Call #2 eligibility check and evaluation process results;
- Section 5 presents SHORE - Open Call #2 selection results and the analytics of the selected projects;
- Section 6 presents overview of SHORE - Open Call #2 selected projects profiles.

1. Background of the SHORE Open Calls

Funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme, SHORE project will support **100 school projects** via **3 Open Calls** and with a **total budget of 900,000€ (max 10,000€ grant per project)** for **primary and secondary schools implementing blue projects** in the pursuit of increasing **ocean and water literacy**, sustainability, and blue economy knowledge among students to mobilise them as agents of change and ramp up the accreditation of [the Network of European Blue Schools](#) of the [EU4Ocean coalition](#).

SHORE's Open Calls are open for schools legally established and based in the European Union or [Horizon Europe Associated Countries](#) from one of the **five target regional areas: Baltic Sea, Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea, Danube River, and Rhine River**.

SHORE-funded projects will support the objectives of the [EU Mission "Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030"](#) and encourage students' active participation and leadership of its low carbon activities, based on [Blue Curricula and Open Schooling Methodologies](#). The school projects should also involve other educators and actors from the school ecosystem and the local community, as well as cooperation/ twinning mechanisms with schools from other locations.

The SHORE Open Calls are open for proposals which include different types of activities from a predefined list, based on the topics about blue economy & ocean literacy, as shown in the Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: SHORE Open Calls Target Topics & Sub-Topics

Selected projects are expected to last up to 6 months, a period during which all school project activities, should be implemented with the funding support received. SHORE Project partners acting as **SHORE Country Hubs** will mentor and guide the schools and students, about successful Blue Skills Curricula and project implementation. Selected projects will benefit through a permanent contact with their mentors, online meetings for project management and sharing of best practices from targeted regions.

Furthermore, SHORE will ensure international visibility and awareness of the projects among the public by creating **its own digital platform**, an open-source virtual learning environment and education management system which will enable the follow-up of student and school projects in addition to publishing developed Blue Skills Curricula materials for school activities and teacher routes. Schools awarded with the grant will have their own profile created at SHORE digital platform, allowing them to upload their activities & share information about their projects. After each open call period, **an online contest** will be held to select the best school projects through a global competition using the said digital platform, and the voting will be open to the public. After the selection of the global winner, the school will be awarded as **“Ocean Ambassador of The Year”** and promoted as such via the SHORE project website and social media.

2. SHORE - Open Call #2 process

SHORE - Open Call #2 was open from **18 September 2024 until 20 November 2024, 5pm CET**. From the programme definition, application and evaluation process to the introduction into SHORE funding programme, SHORE - Open Call #2 has included following steps:

1. Definition of the SHORE Programme (done jointly by all consortium partners) and the preparation of the Open Call #2 documents.
2. Publication of the Open Call #2 on 18 September 2024 after the approval of the Guidelines for Applicants by the Project Officer.
3. Submission of the school project applications at the SHORE submission platform hosted by F6S via the format (application form and SHORE Project Proposal) developed by F6S.
4. Collection, analysis and assessment of submitted applications, process led by F6S and by the Evaluation Board of external evaluators after the Open Call closing date.
5. Open Call #2 applications were sorted and selected following three main steps: 1) Eligibility check 2) Remote proposal evaluation by 2 external experts each 3) Ranking and final selection.
6. Entry of selected applications into the SHORE Programme by signing the Sub-Grant Agreement and accompanying Annexes.

The Figure 2 below presents detailed timeline:

Figure 2: SHORE - Open Call #2 Timeline

3. Applications Analytics

SHORE - Open Call #2 was successfully closed on 20th of November 2024. Applicants submitted 181 applications. The following analytics are based on the applicants answers in their online application form submitted in the SHORE submission platform hosted by F6S.

Number of finalised applications per type of school

When asked to indicate the type of the school applying for the SHORE - Open Call #2, **111 applicants** identified themselves as **secondary schools**, compared to **50 elementary schools** (as shown in Figure 3), making the secondary school the most prominent SHORE - Open Call #2 type of applicant.

*NOTE: 20 applicants identified themselves both as elementary and secondary school in their application form.

Figure 3: SHORE - Open Call #2 No. of finalised applications per type of school

Number of finalised applications based on applicants' accreditation to the Network of European Blue Schools (NEBS)

When asked to indicate the school's accreditation to the Network of European Blue Schools, **41 applicants** answered that the school applying for the SHORE - Open Call #2 is an accredited member, compared to **140 applicants** which aspire to become a member of the Network of European Blue Schools and would submit an application to the Network by the time of completion of the SHORE funded project if selected for funding, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: SHORE - Open Call #2 No. of finalised applications per NEBS accreditation

Number of finalised applications per target areas/country

When asked to indicate the geographical area of the school (according to 5 target areas of SHORE project), the applicants provided following answers, as shown in the Figure 5:

- **100 applicants** selected Mediterranean Sea Area,
- **48 applicants** that selected Black Sea Area,
- **15 applicants** selected Danube River Area,
- **16 applicants** selected Baltic Sea Area,
- **2 applicant** selected Rhine River Area.

Figure 5: SHORE - Open Call #2 No. of finalised applications per target area

When asked to state the country in which the school is legally established, **75 applicants** indicated Türkiye as the school’s country of origin, making them the most prominent group in the SHORE - Open Call #2, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: SHORE - Open Call #2 No. of finalised applications per country of origin

Number of finalised applications per target topic

SHORE Open Call #2 applicants selected at least one target topic and sub-topic of the school’s project. Figure 7 shows the percentage distribution per target topic.

- Topic#1 Sea-based activities (14% based on 55 selections)
- Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter (22% based on 85 selections)
- Topic#3 Biodiversity (28% based on 108 selections)
- Topic#4 Climate Change (17% based on 66 selections)
- Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources (19% based on 71 selections)

Figure 7: SHORE - Open Call #2 Types of finalised applications per target topic in percentages

Referrals statistics

SHORE - Open Call #2 referral statistics are based on the answers from **181 applicants** that opted to answer how they found out about the open call by selecting one or more of the provided options:

- a) Social Media,
- b) Referrals from other EU projects,
- c) European Commission Communications,
- d) F6S website,
- e) SHORE Consortium,
- f) Search Engine,
- g) Event,
- h) Other.

Option “Other” (33%) channel has been the most selected response, followed by “F6S website” (21%), as shown in Figure 8:

Figure 8 SHORE - Open Call #2 Referrals in percentages

For each response selected, applicants elaborated on the specific channel or contact that led them to the open call. For the option “Other” in particular, the most common sources were:

- **Official government communication** (Ministries, Provincial Directorates, Regional School Offices).
- **Academic and research institutions** (universities, marine research centers, NGOs).
- **Word of mouth** (school principals, management offices, colleagues, graduates).
- **Environmental education networks** (Blue Schools, NGO Mare Nostrum, Problue).
- **Online channels** (LinkedIn, newsletters, SHORE website, educational platforms).

4. Evaluation and Eligibility Check Results

4.1 Eligibility Check Phase

The eligibility check of 181 applications was performed according to the rules stated in [Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants](#) and it resulted in **16 non-eligible and 165 eligible** proposals that proceeded into the evaluation phase. The main reasons for ineligibility were following:

- Applying school did not meet the requirement for schools, as the call will fund only projects implemented by primary or secondary schools legally registered and established in EU and/or HEU Associated countries.
- The applicant did not prepare the application in the English language as the official language for the SHORE - Open Call #2.
- The school has received funding from [ProBleu](#) or [BlueLightS](#) project.

4.2 Evaluation Phase

The evaluation phase and final ranking was performed according to the rules stated in [Annex 1 – SHORE Guidelines for Applicants](#), with each proposal being reviewed by 2 external evaluators from the pool of 13 evaluators previously selected as part of SHORE Expression of Interest for Experts [hosted on the F6S platform](#) from 05 February 2024, until 20 March 2024. (first round) and from 30 October 2024, until 20 November 2024. (second round).

The evaluation phase was finalised with following results:

- **30 projects** that received the maximum **5 points** for the final score were selected for the funding.
- **8 projects** that received **4 points** for the final score and fitted into the allocated SHORE - Open Call#2 budget were placed on the reserved list, one school from this list subsequently joined the program after another opted out.
- **135 projects** that received **4 or less points** for the final score and did not fit into the allocated SHORE - Open Call #2 budget were not selected for the funding/reserved list.

5. Selection Results

5.1 Ranking List

SHORE - Open Call #2 was finalised with the selection of 30 school's projects that will receive the funding as part of the project's programme. The following table represents the ranking list of the accepted projects and their beneficiaries.

Table 1 SHORE - Open Call #2 Ranking List

No.	Project Title	Name of the school	Country	Target Region	Target Topic
1	The Future of the Oceans: Protecting Water and Oceans from Waste Oils from Our Homes	Mersin Yenişehir Gelecek Okulları Ortaokulu	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic # 2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter
2	MARBIOLAGO: School students act as scientists for the collection of data on marine biodiversity and the effects of climate change promoting ocean literacy: a case study at the coastal area of Lagonisi, Greece	2nd High School Of Kalivia	Greece	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#4 Climate Change
3	Blue Horizons - from the Danube River to the Oceans	GRG 1 Stubenbastei	Austria	Danube River Area	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#4 Climate Change Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
4	Guardians of the Sea: Empowering Students in Ocean Conservation through STEM and Social Responsibility	Anatolia College	Greece	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter

					Topic#4 Climate Change
5	BLUE DROPS	Ozel Antalya Bahcesehir Bati Ilkokulu	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity
6	WAVES OF CHANGE	Istituto Tecnico Economico e Tecnologico "G.Garibaldi" - Marsala	Italy	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#4 Climate Change Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
7	A.Q.U.A. → Agents Quest United Awareness	Liceul Teoretic International de Informatica Bucuresti	Romania	Black Sea Area	Topic#1 Sea-based activities / Coastal Tourism
8	Healthy Coast, Sustainable Coast	Scoala Gimnaziala Nr. 29 "Mihai Viteazul"	Romania	Black Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
9	From Lunz to the Ocean: a Journey through connected waters	Niederösterreichische Mittelschule Lunz am See	Austria	Danube River Area	Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
10	THE FUTURE OF THE OCEANS : SEAGRASSES	SELİM DİNİZ ORTAOKULU	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#3 Biodiversity
11	WE ARE OCEAN_Nice_Raconter la Mer	Collège Jules ROMAINS	France	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#3 Biodiversity

12	(MEDaverse) Mission to Educate, Discover and Protect: Safeguarding Biodiversity in the Mediterranean	Ano Syros Primary School	Greece	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Topic#3 Biodiversity
13	BLUE TRACE: Awareness and solution-oriented studies for water literacy	Yücel Ballık Ortaokulu	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter
14	The devil is in the details	Budapest X. kerületi Zrínyi Miklós Gimnázium	Hungary	Danube River Area	Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
15	(SOMEK) Student-led Oceanic Movement for Eco-friendly Knowledge	Sömek Ortaokulu	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#3 Biodiversity
16	From Rain to Ocean: Sustainable Water Management and Microplastic Reduction	İzmir Karşıyaka Zeki Şairoğlu Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#4 Climate Change Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
17	(BeBlueActive) Blue Actions for a Sustainable Future-Teaching students to be more active!	1st Primary School of Agios Nikolaos-Crete-Greece	Greece	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
18	(TUROMAP) TURTLES' RoadMap	PRIMARY SCHOOL OF PALEKASTRO	Greece	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity

19	(BlueBoss) Blue Guardians of the Bosphorus	ISTANBUL/BEYKOZ Paşabahçe Secondary School	Turkey	Black Sea Area	Topic#3 Biodiversity
20	Blue Heritage, Blue Future	Fatih Sultan Mehmet Primary School	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#4 Climate Change Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
21	Less Plastic, More Blue	Sehit Mehmet Zengin Secondary School	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic # 2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter
22	(SEA-SPIRIT) Students Engaging in Aquatic Sustainability, Protection, and Innovation for Responsible Tourism	The American College of Greece, Elementary School, Pierce	Greece	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter
23	Water on Watch (WOW): Building a Community of Water Guardians	Plevne Ortaokulu (Plevne Secondary School)	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#4 Climate Change Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
24	WAVE: Water Ambassadors for a Vibrant Environment - Shaping Future Leaders in Sustainable Water Practices	Karahantepe Primary School	Turkey	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources

25	Blue Steps Without Plastic	TERME ORTAOKULU	Turkey	Black Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter
26	Korela's Call: Women of Skyros Uniting for a Cleaner Ocean (KO-WAVE)	SKYROS HIGH SCHOOL	Greece	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic # 2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter
27	Ocean Guardians	Mandoulides Schools	Greece	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic # 2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity
28	Blue Horizons: A wave of awareness for Tomorrows	Hürriyet Secondary School	Turkey	Black Sea Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#4 Climate Change Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
29	Our Oceans, Our Planet. Explore, Protect, Create	Palatul Copiilor Bacau	Romania	Danube River Area	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Topic#3 Biodiversity Topic#4 Climate Change Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources
30	MEDITERRANEAN SEAFOREST at SCHOOL	IC via Padre Semeria	Italy	Mediterranean Sea Area	Topic#4 Climate Change

5.2 Selected Projects Analytics

Number of selected projects per type of school

When asked to indicate the type of the school applying for the **21 projects** selected during SHORE - Open Call #2 comes from secondary schools, compared to **7** coming from elementary schools (as seen in Figure 9), making the secondary school the most populous SHORE Open Call#2 type of applicant.

*NOTE: 2 projects come from the beneficiary which identifies themselves both as elementary and secondary school in their application form.

Figure 9 SHORE - Open Call #2 No. of selected projects per type of school

Number of selected projects based on applicants' accreditation in the Network of European Blue Schools

When asked to indicate the school's accreditation in the Network of European Blue Schools, , 10 school selected for funding during SHORE - Open Call #2 are accredited members, compared to 20 beneficiaries which aspire to become a member of the Network of European Blue Schools and would submit an application to the Network by the time of completion of the SHORE funded project if selected for is funding, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 SHORE - Open Call #2 No. of selected projects per NEBS accreditation

Number of selected projects per target areas /country of origin

SHORE - Open Call #2 school projects will be implemented in the following geographical areas of the school according to 5 target areas of SHORE project in the following numbers, as shown in the Figure 11:

- Mediterranean Sea Area: **21 projects**
- Black Sea Area: **5 projects**
- Danube River Area: **4 projects**

*NOTE: After the evaluation period, Rhine River Area and Baltic Sea Area have no selected projects for SHORE - Open Call #2.

Figure 11 SHORE - Open Call #2 No. of selected projects per target area

13 beneficiaries indicated Türkiye as the school’s country of origin, making them the most populous group in the SHORE Open Call#2, as shown in Figure 12:

Figure 12 SHORE - Open Call #2 No. of selected projects per country of origin

Number of selected projects per target topic

Looking into the percentages based on the individual selections, Figure 13 shows the distribution of SHORE Open Call #2 selected project per target topic in the following manner:

- Topic#1 Sea-based activities (12% based on 8 selections)
- Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter (29% based on 20 selections)
- Topic#3 Biodiversity (26% based on 18 selections)
- Topic#4 Climate Change (15% based on 10 selections)
- Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources (18% based on 12 selections)

Figure 13 SHORE - Open Call #2 types of selected projects per target topic in percentages

6. Selected Projects' Profiles

1. The Future of the Oceans: Protecting Water and Oceans from Waste Oils from Our Homes	
School Name	Mersin Yenişehir Gelecek Okulları Ortaokulu
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Sub-topics: Various Wastes from Cities
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

The Future of the Oceans: Protecting Water and Oceans from Waste Oils from Our Homes Project aims to help students understand the impact of the ocean on people and our impact on the ocean in order to maintain and improve the health of our oceans and waters through sustainable management of the ocean. In this context, activities were carried out to reduce the impact of domestic waste oils, one of the main pollutants, on water resources and oceans. For this purpose, Mersin Yenişehir Future Secondary School, together with its teachers and administrators, cooperates with 16 local, regional, national and international institutions. Project activities will be carried out in Mersin / Turkey between February and July 2025. At the end of the project activities, individuals will have knowledge about the problems of the oceans and at the same time, people will have progressed in their ability to protect, preserve, use and manage marine resources sustainably.

2. MARBIOLAGO School students act as scientists for the collection of data on marine biodiversity and the effects of climate change promoting ocean literacy: a case study at the coastal area of Lagonisi, Greece	
School Name	2nd High School Of Kalivia
Country of Origin	Greece
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in waters Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Eutrophication, Rising Temperature, Droughts, Rise in Sea Levels
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

This proposal aims to conduct a comprehensive biodiversity survey of the Lagonisi coastline (Attica, Greece). Its coastal habitat consists of different substrates, like sand, rocks, beachrocks, cliffs, Posidonia meadows, etc, suitable habitats for a great variety of marine organisms. The survey will engage school students and their teachers, marine scientists from various research directions (biologists, physicists, geologists, etc), and stakeholders including the , and the local community. Employing innovative yet simple scientific methodologies and techniques, school students will be able to explore the biodiversity in the shallow embayment of their coastline, aiming to assess the various environmental, namely physical (SST, sea level changes on monthly/seasonal scales), biological (microorganisms, plankton, Posidonia fields) components as well as biogeochemical processes (nutrient stocks and the CO₂/ carbonate system).

3. Blue Horizons - from the Danube River to the Oceans	
School Name	GRG 1 Stubenbastei
Country of Origin	Austria
Target SHORE Area	Danube River Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities – Sub-topics: Fisheries and Aquaculture Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Migration of the Species, Damage to Coral Reefs and Riverbeds, Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals, Preserve biodiversity in waters Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Rising Temperature, Droughts, Rise in Sea Levels Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Drinking water, Food from sea and water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Our project aims to provide integrated, hands-on learning experiences that connect biology, ecology, environmental science, geography, chemistry, and mathematics in real-world contexts. Through field trips to national parks and marine ecosystems, students will study ecosystems, analyze water quality, and identify species, linking scientific concepts with practical observations. In the lab, students will conduct experiments on water quality, pollution, and sustainability, applying chemistry and environmental science to real-world challenges such as testing water samples and analyzing pollutants. They will also use math to analyze data, create graphs, and calculate measurements, strengthening their skills in addressing issues like pollution and species population assessment. The project will foster the development of communication skills through presentations, group discussions, and informational materials. Senior students will mentor younger peers during field trips, promoting teamwork.

4. Guardians of the Sea: Empowering Students in Ocean Conservation through STEM and Social Responsibility	
School Name	Anatolia College
Country of Origin	Greece
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities – Sub-topics: Coastal Tourism Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics, Various Wastes from Cities Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Water-body acidification
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

The project empowers students 12-16 to address marine conservation challenges by combining STEM, social responsibility, and innovative thinking, centered on the "Guardian of the Sea" submarine. By building on existing initiatives, the project equips teachers and students with the tools and resources to explore ocean literacy, develop solutions for underwater plastic pollution, and foster environmental stewardship. Students will learn to think critically and creatively while applying STEM skills to real-world problems, with a strong emphasis on human-centered approaches. Through teacher training and classroom activities, the project nurtures young ambassadors for ocean conservation who inspire their peers and communities. The project culminates in the Sea of Ideas Hackathon, where students collaborate and present innovative solutions to marine challenges. The project amplifies its impact through broad dissemination efforts, inspiring collective action.

5. BLUE DROPS	
School Name	Ozel Antalya Bahcesehir Bati Ilkokulu
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in waters
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

This project offers hands-on learning experiences to enhance ocean literacy among students and the community. Research shows that outdoor activities and real-world projects boost environmental awareness and engagement in students (Ballantyne & Packer, 2009). The project aims to equip students with the skills to understand and protect water ecosystems through outdoor activities, laboratory work, and creative workshops. In line with the European Union's "Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030" mission, these activities raise awareness about marine pollution and promote sustainable solutions. STEM-focused tasks like analyzing water samples and pollution timelines form a significant educational model. Mini museum and aquarium setups are supported by open teaching methods that foster leadership skills. The project's impact will be promoted through local media, social media, and partnerships.

6. WAVES OF CHANGE	
School Name	Istituto Tecnico Economico e Tecnologico "G.Garibaldi" - Marsala
Country of Origin	Italy
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics, Various Wastes from Cities Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Erosion and Flooding, Preserve biodiversity in waters Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Water-body acidification Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Drinking water, Food from sea and water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

The initiative aims to create a literacy path to support the dissemination of the relevant principles on the three missions of the ocean with the participation of students and a collaboration network in the Sicilian territory. The actions are implemented in a multidisciplinary way through seminars, workshops, laboratory visits, beach cleanups and many others, in line with the EU strategy on biodiversity 2030; the actions aim to contribute to the knowledge and activation of ethical behaviors functional to the prevention of pollution of our oceans in line with the European Action Plan, especially to make the school plastic free and encourage other schools in this process. The "Waves of Change" project proposes the installation of water dispensers in the school, aluminium water bottles giveaway and territorial dissemination to raise awareness among children and citizens on the management of water resources, where students become active subjects in the dissemination of good practices.

7. A.Q.U.A. → Agents Quest United Awareness	
School Name	Liceul Teoretic International de Informatica Bucuresti
Country of Origin	Romania
Target SHORE Area	Black Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Sub-topics: Coastal Tourism
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

A.Q.U.A.- Agents Quest Unity Awareness empowers students as agents of change to promote sustainable coastal tourism and ocean literacy through engaging sea-based activities, transforming them into guardians of the Black Sea and inspiring change locally and across Europe. Connecting our school in Bucharest with partner schools in Constanța, Romania, and Varna, Bulgaria, the project fosters cross-border collaboration. Over six months, students lead impactful activities such as MeetNTalks, training sessions and webinars on sustainable tourism, field trips, coastal cleanups, boat activities, a 90-second video competition, a European A.Q.U.A. Storybook and an International A.Q.U.A. Conference attended by students, local communities, European Parliament members, and covered extensively by mass media. As a certified European Blue School, we build further partnerships and contribute to the European Mission to Restore Our Oceans and Waters by 2030, fostering united awareness and ongoing impact.

8. Healthy Coast, Sustainable Coast	
School Name	Scoala Gimnaziala Nr. 29 "Mihai Viteazul"
Country of Origin	Romania
Target SHORE Area	Black Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities Sub-topics: Coastal Tourism
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

This is a project about Ocean's and sea's influence on us and our influence on the waters. The project is meant to engage the students' participation on the principles of Project Based Learning Education: They will work in groups to experience and explore relevant, real-world problems, questions, issues and challenges; they will create presentations and products to share what they have learned. They will carry out the activities and communicate with each other by using all kinds of ICT tools. They will interact to each other and get in touch with different cultures and realities. The teachers will monitor and guide the students while they also will collaborate with the colleagues from the partner schools as well. They will learn new things together with their students. Throughout the project, all partners will have a detailed planning and ongoing evaluation of the procedure acting together for a better water environment and increase the awareness on the problems of the marine life .

9. From Lunz to the Ocean: a Journey through connected waters	
School Name	Niederösterreichische Mittelschule Lunz am See
Country of Origin	Austria
Target SHORE Area	Danube River Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in waters Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Nuclear power plants on shores
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Although far from the sea, Mittelschule Lunz am See is dedicated to ocean protection by educating students about the link between freshwater ecosystems and the ocean. Through exploring local water bodies like Lunzer Seebach, Lake Lunz, and nearby rivers, students learn about biodiversity, ecosystem services, and conservation needs. Our project highlights the source-to-sea continuum, fostering a holistic view of water systems. Using innovative approaches like field trips, workshops, and peer learning, students lead tasks, present findings, and engage with the community. They will also share their learning with our partner school in Romania. Collaborations with WasserCluster Lunz, Haus der Wildnis, and the local wastewater plant provide scientific knowledge and practical insights. This partnership cultivates a new generation of water-literate citizens and promotes European cooperation through partnerships with other Blue Schools and marine organizations like MareMundi.

10. (FU.SE.) THE FUTURE OF THE OCEANS : SEAGRASSES	
School Name	SELİM DİNİZ ORTAOKULU
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#3 Biodiversity Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in waters
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Creatures in the oceans have an important place in the delicate ecological balance of the world. Seagrass, one of these living species, produces more organic matter than tropical forests, breathes life into our seas with the oxygen it produces, hosts many living creatures and hosts them to reproduce. Seagrasses receive the most damage when their roots are uprooted as a result of boat anchors rubbing against the seabed. In order to prevent this destruction, our project aims to build an ecological buoy and leave the buoy in places frequented by tour boats. In this way, the habitats of the seagrasses at the bottom of the sea remain intact and many creatures hosted by the sea meadows can continue their lives and the sustainability of biodiversity continues. It is also planned to go to the Oceanographic aquarium in Valencia to observe the biodiversity in different waters and learn what is being done to protect it.

11. (WAO NICE) WE ARE OCEAN_Nice_Raconter la Mer	
School Name	Collège Jules ROMAINS
Country of Origin	France
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Damage to Coral Reefs and Riverbeds, Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals, Erosion and Flooding, Preserve biodiversity in waters
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

WAO Nice brings interdisciplinary art-science workshops to the College Jules Romains. The artist Morgane Ganault together with marine biologists and curators from ARTPORT_making waves co-create a comic strip project based on the presented marine and water research around the topics:

- The estuary and the encounter between fresh and salt water, with the example of the river Roya leading to the Mediterranean Sea.
- inversions between underwater and terrestrial landscapes
- The fauna at the estuary: who are these beings in between?
- The human influence on health and biodiversity as well as preservation

12. (MEDaverse) Mission to Educate, Discover and Protect: Safeguarding Biodiversity in the Mediterranean	
School Name	Ano Syros Primary School
Country of Origin	Greece
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities – Sub-topics: Coastal Tourism Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals, Preserve biodiversity in waters
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

MEDaverse fosters marine literacy and environmental stewardship to preserve Mediterranean biodiversity through hands-on activities such as coastal field research, water and microplastic analysis, expert workshops, and beach clean-ups. Students gain a deep understanding of marine ecosystems and participate in an immersive boat expedition to the island of Gyaros, and a field trip to Naxos. These experiences offer valuable insights into vital habitats and enable students to identify contemporary threats to biodiversity protection and conservation priorities. Collaboration with environmental institutions and the local community promotes awareness and action. The project's impact is further amplified through eTwinning partnerships promoting European cooperation and a dynamic video campaign on TikTok and YouTube. MEDaverse aligns with the EU's Mission Ocean, inspiring young citizens to protect the Mediterranean's biodiversity and advocate for a sustainable, resilient marine environment.

13. BLUE TRACE: Awareness and solution-oriented studies for water literacy	
School Name	Yücel Ballık Ortaokulu
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

This project is an environmental education and awareness project for students aged 11-14. With this project to be carried out in Sakarya, it is aimed for students to learn about environmental issues such as hazardous substances, marine litter, plastics and microplastics and to increase their water literacy. Throughout the project, students will learn the importance of protecting water ecosystems through interactive presentations, nature walks, waste collection activities, laboratory experiments and practical activities such as water sampling. Students will also work on recycling by adopting zero-waste approaches and develop solution-oriented projects against plastic pollution. At the end of the project, students will present their own solution proposals for the sustainable management of water resources and organize a final exhibition where they will exhibit their individual contributions to the environment.

14. The devil is in the details	
School Name	Budapest X. kerületi Zrínyi Miklós Gimnázium
Country of Origin	Hungary
Target SHORE Area	Danube River Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources Sub-topics: Drinking water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

During our project we examine the quality of drinking water in different environments. In Budapest, along the Danube, we will test the quality of water the population has access to in the capital environment. In Balan in Transylvania let's see what kind of water quality we can experience in a mountainous village environment close to springs and natural beauties. While in the Danube delta region we can observe what results we get at the meeting of a large river and the sea. The results of our tests are compared, summarized and finally shared with a wider audience in an exhibition. Our goal is to use our project to draw attention to social responsibility and encourage young people to be more careful in their everyday activities. With our attitude-shaping activity, we contribute to the achievement of the European climate goals, especially to the improvement of water purity and the reduction of carbon dioxide emission.

15. (SOMEK) Student-led Oceanic Movement for Eco-friendly Knowledge	
School Name	Sömek Ortaokulu
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#3 Biodiversity Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in waters
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Sömek Middle School is located in Silifke with 53 students and 10 staff. The name of our project is "Student-led Oceanic Movement for Eco-friendly Knowledge" and its acronym is SOMEK. We wanted the project acronym to be the same as the name of our school and the village where the school is located. Because we wanted the project to be embraced. Silifke is home to the Göksu River and Göksu Delta. Göksu River flows into the Mediterranean through the Göksu Delta it forms. Considering the existing water and sea potential of Silifke, with our SOMEK project that we will start from SÖMEK Middle School, an oceanic movement to protect biodiversity will be initiated for the Göksu River, Göksu Delta and the Mediterranean for eco friendly knowledge under the leadership of our students. Meetings, trainings, field and museum trips and exhibitions will be held to protect and restore marine and freshwaters, ecosystems and biodiversity by eliminating the damages that people caused.

16. From Rain to Ocean: Sustainable Water Management and Microplastic Reduction	
School Name	İzmir Karşıyaka Zeki Şairoğlu Vocational and Technical Anatolian High School
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics, Various Wastes from Cities Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals, Preserve biodiversity in waters Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Droughts Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Renewable Marine and Water Energy, Drinking water, Food from sea and water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

This project aims to reduce the effects of microplastic pollution on aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, contribute to the protection of ocean ecosystems with sustainable water management practices, and encourage environmentally friendly water use in local agriculture. It is aimed to prevent the transport of microplastics and increase natural filtration with rainwater collection systems. Collected rainwater A collection infrastructure will be created and the collected water will be used in environmentally friendly practices such as organic agriculture and vegetable beds in the school garden. The project will raise awareness of ocean literacy and inspire sustainable water management strategies by pioneering the protection of marine ecosystems, increasing biodiversity and widespread use of environmentally friendly water in agriculture.

17. (BeBlueActive) Blue Actions for a Sustainable Future- Teaching students to be more active!	
School Name	1st Primary School of Agios Nikolaos-Crete-Greece
Country of Origin	Greece
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities – Sub-topics: Coastal Tourism Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Renewable Marine and Water Energy, Drinking water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Objectives:

- 1.Environmental awareness
- 2.Knowledge of scientific observation and analysis methods
- 3.Career orientation
- 4. Recognition of cultural heritage
- 5.Development of creative thinking,collaboration,and presentation skills.

Activities:

- 1: Observation of the Almyros Ecosystem / Impact of Tourism
- 2: The Value of the Sea and Water through History and Literature
- 3: Microplastics / Seas and Water Purification
- 4: Careers Related to Energy / Water
- 5: Collaboration with the Municipal Marina of Agios Nikolaos

Output Materials: Model of an Ecosystem, Digital Collection of Creative Writing contest, Educational Kit, Multimedia Presentation and digital photo album, Professions board game, Padlet with informational materials , Digital Guide for model sustainable marinas.

Results:

- Articles, photos, videos, newsletters of workshops will be uploaded to the blog of our school and YouTube channel, Creation of a new site for this project, celebrate World Ocean Day, Open event at at the end of the project.

18. TUROMAP: TURTLES' Road Map	
School Name	PRIMARY SCHOOL OF PALEKASTRO
Country of Origin	Greece
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities – Sub-topics: Coastal Tourism Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Various Wastes from Cities Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in waters
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Main Objective:

The project aims to promote awareness and proactive measures to protect turtle populations by addressing the challenges they face, such as habitat loss, pollution, and climate change.

Expected Results:

- Development of an educational framework for turtle conservation, including lesson plans, activities, and interactive resources.
- Creation of an actionable "Turtles' Road Map" outlining conservation strategies, including habitat restoration, pollution reduction, and public awareness campaigns.
- Enhanced awareness among students, educators, and communities about the ecological importance of turtles.
- Collection and sharing of data on local turtle populations and habitats through a collaborative network.
- Implementation of turtle-friendly actions, such as cleanup drives, monitoring nesting sites, and reducing single-use plastics.
- Impact
- Environmental Impact
- Educational Impact

19. (BlueBoss) Blue Guardians of the Bosphorus	
School Name	ISTANBUL/BEYKOZ Paşabahçe Secondary School
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Black Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#3 Biodiversity Sub-topics: Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals, Preserve biodiversity in waters
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Our project unites students, teachers, and the local community to explore and protect the unique biodiversity of the Istanbul Strait (Bosphorus). Students from Paşabahçe Middle School will collaborate with scientists from TÜBİTAK Marmara Research Center to conduct comprehensive water quality analyses, studying the effects of microplastic pollution on marine life. By engaging in hands-on research, students will contribute to real environmental studies. In partnership with Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality and Beykoz Municipality, we will organize coastal cleanup activities involving students, parents—many from socio-economically disadvantaged backgrounds—and local residents to raise awareness about protecting aquatic environments. The project will culminate in a public exhibition where students will showcase their work, share findings, and propose solutions, also engaging with the European Network of Blue Schools to foster broader impact through shared experiences.

20. Blue Heritage, Blue Future	
School Name	Fatih Sultan Mehmet Primary School
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities – Sub-topics: Marine and River Transport and Shipping, Water Sports Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Damage to Coral Reefs and Riverbeds, Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals, Preserve biodiversity in waters Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Rising Temperature Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Renewable Marine and Water Energy, Drinking water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Water is one of the basic elements of life. It is of critical importance for the protection and balance of ecosystems. Therefore, it is important to raise public awareness for the protection and sustainable use of water. This project will be carried out with 4 managers, 39 teachers, 2 PIKTES class, 1247 students in grades 1-2-3 and 4. Collaboration will be made with local governments, NGOs, public institutions and organizations and European Blue Schools. Activities will be carried out in different learning environments through “trainings, exhibitions, webinars, laboratory testing and analysis of results, virtual educational activities, museum trips, field trips, local expeditions, boat” activities. With the activities to be held in public areas, awareness about water will be increased, clean and healthy water will be left for future generations and the protection of ecosystems and biodiversity will be ensured.

21. Less Plastic, More Blue	
School Name	Sehit Mehmet Zengin Secondary School
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Based on the EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, the project emphasizes the interconnectedness of local actions and global water systems, even though our school is inland. Through workshops, field trips and AR/VR technology, students will learn about marine ecosystems, plastic pollution, microplastics and sustainability. Activities include clean-up events, expert talks and art projects that promote environmental responsibility. The project aims to instill lasting awareness and promote sustainable behavior within the school and the wider community.

22. (SEA-SPIRIT) Students Engaging in Aquatic Sustainability, Protection, and Innovation for Responsible Tourism	
School Name	The American College of Greece, Elementary School, Pierce
Country of Origin	Greece
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#1 Sea-based activities – Sub-topics: Coastal Tourism, Marine and River Transport and Shipping Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Various Wastes from Cruise Ships
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

The SEA-SPIRIT project aims to integrate environmental education into the elementary school curriculum through a series of innovative, interactive, and interdisciplinary activities. By engaging students in hands-on learning experiences, the project seeks to raise awareness about the importance of marine conservation and sustainable tourism. The main objective is to educate and empower students to become active participants in environmental protection and adoption of sustainable practices. Students will not only acquire knowledge but also develop critical thinking, leadership, and collaborative skills via the creation of student-led initiatives and activities. SEA-SPIRIT will create a generation of environmentally conscious individuals who are equipped to influence the positively the future. By engaging with the local community and stakeholders, the project will promote a collaborative effort towards preserving the health of our oceans and ensuring the sustainability of coastal tourism.

23. Water on Watch (WOW): Building a Community of Water Guardians	
School Name	Plevne Ortaokulu (Plevne Secondary School)
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in waters Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Droughts Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Renewable Marine and Water Energy, Drinking water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

One of our main goals is to raise awareness among our students about the effects of the global climate crisis on water resources and to increase their water literacy, thus enabling them to take on the role of water guardians. Within the scope of this project, we will collaborate with a school in Romania, where we realized an eTwinning project on “water stress” last year, and visit Gimnaziala George Calinescu Onesti, a Blue School labeled school. The project will include hands-on workshops on water filtration, rainwater harvesting and water saving techniques. Students will also participate in local observation activities to conduct field studies on water pollution and the use of water resources. Furthermore, environmental awareness events will be organized in cooperation with local authorities to promote water conservation in the community. Ultimately, students' environmental awareness will increase and this awareness will spread to the wider community, creating a long-term impact.

24. WAVE: Water Ambassadors for a Vibrant Environment - Shaping Future Leaders in Sustainable Water Practices	
School Name	Karahantepe Primary School
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Black Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in waters Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Droughts Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Renewable Marine and Water Energy, Drinking water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

The “WAVE: Water Ambassadors for a Vibrant Environment” project empowers 4th-grade students at Karahantepe Primary School in Şanlıurfa to become leaders in water conservation. Using AR/VR, students will explore the water cycle, pollution, and the effects of climate change. They will create water-saving solutions and lead community outreach as Water Ambassadors.

The project includes field trips to coastal areas, where students will observe marine ecosystems and understand the impact of pollution. The Water Ambassadors will educate peers, families, and the community about sustainable practices.

Expected outcomes: Improved water literacy and sustainable habits.

25. Blue Steps Without Plastic	
School Name	TERME ORTAOKULU
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Black Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

Blue Steps aims to raise awareness of environmental sustainability and strengthen individual responsibility by increasing students' ocean and water literacy. Focusing on combating plastic pollution, the project aims to raise environmentally sensitive individuals by involving students in activities such as plastic waste collection, microplastic analysis, recycling and upcycling processes. The activities will enable students to discover the effects of plastic pollution on the environment, develop solution-oriented thinking skills and take environmental responsibility. Students will actively participate in scientific and creative processes through activities such as microplastic analysis, recycling facility visits, beach cleaning and design competitions. The project is expected to contribute to students becoming individuals who are sensitive to environmental problems at local and global levels, to the protection of ocean ecosystems and to environmental sustainability goals.

26. Korela's Call: Women of Skyros Uniting for a Cleaner Ocean (KO-WAVE)	
School Name	SKYROS HIGH SCHOOL
Country of Origin	Greece
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Heavy Metals, Plastics & Microplastics, Various Wastes from Cruise Ships, Various Wastes from Cities
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

KO-WAVE engages students, local female entrepreneurs, and community members in activities merging art, circular economy, and environmental awareness through a week-long community event to protect the ocean in Skyros. Guided by local artists and female entrepreneurs, students will create an upcycled art installation to beautify their neighborhood while participating in workshops on sustainability and eco-innovation, strengthening community bonds, fostering environmental awareness and community-driven initiatives. KO-WAVE is the result of a collaboration inspired by the methodology of the SEA'sters program of Positive LAB, adapting its core principles to the unique local context of Skyros, within the framework of the Skyros Project. The project highlights the critical role of women in ocean stewardship and aims to explore, through Korela, the need to foster female eco-leadership to drive the transition toward sustainability.

27. Ocean Guardians	
School Name	Mandoulides Schools
Country of Origin	Greece
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Heavy Metals, Plastics & Microplastics, Various Wastes from Cities Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Migration of the Species, Microplastics Uptake by Aquatic Animals, Preserve biodiversity in waters
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

The Ocean Guardians project inspires students to become Ocean Guardians, combining hands-on environmental activities with creative learning to protect marine ecosystems. Through beach cleanups in Thessaloniki, students will actively remove litter, categorize waste, and explore the impact of pollution on marine biodiversity. Interactive workshops with experts will teach the importance of sustainable practices and how to transform waste into innovative creations. The project concludes with a vibrant public exhibition, showcasing student-made artwork and raising community awareness. By engaging young learners and fostering ocean literacy, BLUEIMPACT supports the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030" while nurturing the next generation of environmental leaders.

28. Blue Horizons: A wave of awareness for Tomorrows	
School Name	Hürriyet Secondary School
Country of Origin	Türkiye
Target SHORE Area	Black Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Various Wastes from Cities Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Water-body acidification Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Drinking water, Food from sea and water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

"Blue Horizons:A wave of awareness for tomorrows" project aims to raise awareness about water conservation among students and the local community in Düzce. Through activities like water-saving projects, local water source investigations, beach cleanups, and creative workshops, students will engage in hands-on learning. Expected outcomes include enhanced water literacy, active environmental participation, and creative outputs such as artwork and social media campaigns. The project ends up in a community-wide event showing all efforts and promoting sustainable water use. The initiative aligns with SHORE's goal of improving water conservation awareness.

29. Our Oceans, Our Planet. Explore, Protect, Create	
School Name	Palatul Copiilor Bacau
Country of Origin	Romania
Target SHORE Area	Danube River Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#2 Hazardous Substances and Marine Litter – Sub-topics: Plastics & Microplastics, Various Wastes from Cities Topic#3 Biodiversity – Sub-topics: Preserve biodiversity in Waters Topic#4 Climate Change – Sub-topics: Water-body acidification, Rising Temperature, Rise in Sea Levels Topic#5 Sustainable Use of Water Resources – Sub-topics: Drinking water
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

We are a school for extra-curricular activities which are chosen by parents and students for spare time of their pupils. Besides artistic and sportive clubs in our school are in working environmental education clubs. In this project, students with ages from 8-16 years old will be involved. The proposal includes a comprehensive Blue Calendar of activities integrated into the school curriculum of these environmental clubs, focusing on ocean and water literacy, and aligned with the EU Mission Ocean & Waters. Situated between two big rivers, Bistrita and Siret, Bacau city has beautiful surroundings, rich in biodiversity which have to be protected. The awareness about climate change will be increased through transdisciplinary approaches: field trips, museum visit, experiments, interactive sessions, games, accessing measurements made by satellites, community involvement, STEAM activities, volunteering campaigns. An eTwinning project will be conducted with other European schools, NEBS members.

30. (MED_SEA4_SCHOOL) MEDITERRANEAN SEAFOREST at SCHOOL	
School Name	IC via Padre Semeria
Country of Origin	Italy
Target SHORE Area	Mediterranean Sea Area
Target Topic / Sub-Topic	Topic#4 Climate Change Sub-topics: Rising Temperature
Project Duration	up to 6 months
Date of the Award	17 January 2025.

Project Description:

The project aims at deepening the knowledge of the Posidonia seagrass beds only found in our Mediterranean seas and the fundamental role they play for the marine ecosystem through the involvement of students/teachers in different activities - both in school and at the beach – by means of students as the key drivers of change for nature preservation for a successful fight for climate change and strengthen sea’s health revival. Moreover, the project will focus on raising awareness on the benquettes as an environmental resource to be protected and left on the beach: to this end, the implementation of the Project will strengthen the knowledge phase by bringing the Mediterranean Sea into the classrooms and stimulate a sustainable and eco-friendly tourism of the beaches by using new and innovative teaching and learning resources – i.e. the setting up of a virtual digital museum where each student and related families as well as other Blue Schools Network may access to).

SHORE

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